

Rarest of the Rare: Pulmonary Tuberculosis with Mediastinal Emphysema and Cachexia: A Case Report**Dhirendra Nath Majhi¹, Rajesh A Shetty², Ravi Nimonkar³, Maninder Pal Singh Pardal⁴**¹Associate Professor, Dept. of Medicine, Armed Forces Medical Services, India,²Associate Professor, Dept. of Community Medicine, Armed Forces Medical Services, India,^{3,4}Professor, Dept. of Community Medicine, Armed Forces Medical Services, India

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Abstract:

Pneumomediastinum is a very rare presentation of pulmonary tuberculosis and can pose great challenges in the diagnosis and management of the patient. Children comprise a significant proportion of the global TB caseload, and experience considerable TB-related morbidity and mortality. The subtle signs of disease may delay the diagnosis and consequently progression to a significantly more devastating form. Our case of disseminated tuberculosis presenting with features of pneumomediastinum was subjected to detailed history taking, clinical examination and relevant investigations. History of anorexia, weight loss and low grade fever was elicited. On clinical examination patient was found to have BMI of 10.28 kg/m². Other features of malnutrition such as cheilosis, loss of buccal fat, saggy skin, sunken eyes, gross muscle wasting, skeletal prominence in thoracic cage, and scaphoid abdomen were marked. Bilateral subcentimetric cervical lymphadenopathy; and kyphosis were also observed. Chest examination revealed mild volume loss and few basal crepitations on right side. Imaging revealed multiple air bubbles in the neck, extending within the retro pharyngeal, parapharyngeal, prevertebral and carotid spaces, extending inferiorly into the superior and middle mediastinum, and into the neural foramina on the right at the level of C5 vertebra. Sub segmental Fibrobronchiectatic changes with bronchiolitis within the posterior basal segment of bilateral lower lobe; and few cavitory lesions were observed in the right lower lobe with one of the lesions having developed direct communication into the mediastinal cavity. On laboratory investigations, differential leucocyte count, platelet count were deranged, Serum calcium, serum potassium, serum phosphorus, total proteins, and LDH were also deranged. Testosterone, T3, T4 and ACTH were reduced, while CEA was raised. Based on the clinical and laboratory profile, a diagnosis of Disseminated Tuberculosis with secondary hypocortisolism was made. Patient was managed with weight based antitubercular drugs as per national guidelines, levothyroxin, low dose steroid and other supportive therapy. Patient was discharged after around 15 days of hospitalisation. Patient was followed up every month to monitor progress of his clinical condition. He gradually started eating with exercise tolerance of 5 kms; and normal liver function tests. His evaluation after two months of completion of ATT revealed, he is cheerful, going to school, started studying, regularly eating homemade food and gained 22 kg of weight and his parents were also relieved of their anxiety.

Keywords: Pneumomediastinum, Tuberculosis, Anorexia, Bronchiolitis.

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Introduction

The term mediastinal emphysema also known as pneumomediastinum was first described by Laënnec in 1819 and is defined as the presence of free air in the mediastinal cavity. [1,2]

It is classified into two types, one is spontaneous pneumomediastinum without a definite aetiology; and the other is secondary pneumomediastinum as a consequence of trauma, underlying disease or iatrogenic due to any therapeutic procedures. Pneumomediastinum is a very rare presentation of pulmonary tuberculosis and can pose great

challenges in the in the diagnosis and management of the patient. [1,3] Children comprise a significant proportion of the global TB caseload, and experience considerable TB-related morbidity and mortality. The subtle signs of disease may delay the diagnosis and consequently compound the risk of disease progression to a significantly more devastating form. [4] Here, we present a unique and unusual case of disseminated tuberculosis in a 14-year old male with no known comorbidities, who

presented with features of pneumomediastinum in the outpatient department of our hospital.

The pneumomediastinum was secondary to direct communication of cavitary tuberculosis lesion of right lower lobe into the mediastinal cavity. In this instant case the presence of pneumomediastinum was diagnosed before the presence of pulmonary tuberculosis was suspected and subsequently demonstrated.

Case report:

History: This 14 years old son of a government employee, studying in 8th standard, gradually lost interest in his studies, stopped eating properly, isolated himself from his friends circle and remained sleeping at home most of the time. There was a history of low grade fever for two months, for which he was given paracetamol off and on. Later he developed reduced appetite and weight loss from 40 kg to 20 kg over a period of two months. He consulted many doctors including physicians, ENT specialist, gastroenterologist and psychiatrist for his problems without any definite relief. Patient reported to the medical outpatient department of a large tertiary care hospital in North India, with one person support on a wheelchair as he was not able to stand properly. History of not eating properly since last two months, nausea and vomiting whatever he was eating was given by the patient's mother. He was admitted to the acute medical ward of our hospital.

Clinical examination: Clinically he was thin built, hyporesponsive to questions asked; and remained silent most of the time, His weight was 28 kg and height was 165 cm with BMI of 10.28 kg/m². Features of malnutrition with cheilosis, loss of buccal fat of pad, saggy skin were observed, hypopigmentation, hyperpigmentation; and neurocutaneous markers were conspicuous by their absence, while skin fold thickness over triceps was 5 mm. There were no bed sores, but sunken eyes, gross muscle wasting in all limbs, skeletal prominence in thoracic cage, scaphoid abdomen and pallor were observed., Bilateral subcentimetric cervical lymphadenopathy, kyphosis and drooping neck were other relevant findings. Trachea was central, air entry was bilaterally equal, chest expansion was only 3 cm with equal movements on both sides with mild volume loss and few basal crepitations on right side. There was no hepatosplenomegaly, abdominal mass or ascites, On examination of higher mental functions, patient looked depressed, gag reflex was sluggish, but rest of the cranial nerve examinations were within normal limits. He was walking with small steps, had both proximal and distal muscle wasting with

near absent deep tendon jerks; and bilateral plantars were flexor. Sensory system and other clinical examinations were within normal limits. Based on above history and clinical findings a provisional diagnosis of cachexia with lymphadenopathy with possible lower lobe bronchiolitis was considered. Following differential diagnosis were considered:

- a) Disseminated Tuberculosis
- b) Hypocortisolism
- c) Malignancies
- d) Severe depression
- e) Anorexia nervosa
- f) HIV infection

Investigations: CECT chest and abdomen revealed multiple air bubbles in the neck, extending within the retro pharyngeal, parapharyngeal, prevertebral and carotid spaces, extending inferiorly into the superior and middle mediastinum. Air was also seen extending into the neural foramina on the right at the level of C5 vertebra, within the neck space and tracking into the mediastinum with no definite evidence of aerodigestive tract leak, Sub segmental fibrobronchiectatic changes with bronchiolitis within the posterior basal segment of bilateral lower lobe (right more than left) likely secondary to aspiration was also observed. Few cavitary lesions were observed in the right lower lobe with one of the lesions having developed direct communication into the mediastinal cavity. Trachea and bronchi were normal. No abnormal findings were noted in the abdomen.

CECT chest and abdomen (repeated after 10 days) near complete resolution of pneumomediastinum with air in retropharyngeal space in neck, bilateral pulmonary interstitial emphysema without any intraparenchymal lesion or associated pneumothorax.. Few air pockets were noted along the precarinal and sub cardinal segments of oesophagus. Significant resolution of extensive air within the mediastinum as well as the neck was also observed. No other parenchymal lung cysts/ bronchiectasis/consolidations were noted. Rest of the lung fields were normal. No significant mediastinal or hilar lymphadenopathy was observed. No abnormal findings were noted in the abdomen.

MRI brain revealed mild generalised brain atrophy with cerebral and cerebellar volume loss was noted with prominent cisterns and sulcal space. UGI endoscopy revealed Pangastritis.

Laboratory investigations are tabulated in Table 1. Photographs of CECT chest done at the time of admission and after 10 days are presented in Figures 1 and 2 respectively.

Table 1: Laboratory investigation reports of the case

Investigation	Report on date of admission	Report after one month of ATT	Normal values [5,6,7,8,9,10]
Haematology			
Hb%	12.9 gm/dl	13.4gm/dl	12.4 - 15.7 gm/dl
RBCs	4.67 x 10 ⁶ /mm ³	5.1 x 10 ⁶ /mm ³	4.2 - 5.3 x 10 ⁶ /mm ³
WBCs	6130/ul	5230/ul	3800 - 10400/ul
DLC			
Neutrophils	55.50%	58.30%	39 - 75%
Lymphocytes	38.60%	36.30%	25 - 45%
Monocytes	2.70%*	3.70%	3 - 6%
Eosinophils	2.60%	1.20%	0 - 3%
Basophils	0.60%	0.50%	0 - 1%
Platelets	123x10³/ul*	260x10 ³ /ul	138.7 - 319.6 x 10 ³ /ul
Neutrophils(absolute count)	3.41x10 ³ /ul	3.05x10 ³ /ul	1.4 - 6.1 x 10 ³ /ul
Monocyte(absolute count)	2.37x 10³/ul*	0.19x10 ³ /ul/ul	0.2 - 0.8 x 10 ³ /ul
Eosinophils (absolute count)	0.15x10 ³ /ul	0.06x10 ³ /ul	0.1 - 0.2 x 10 ³ /ul
MCV	81.6 fl	93.2 fl	79.9 - 93.0 fl
MCH	27.6pg	28.4 pg	26.3 - 31.7 pg
MCHC	33.8gm/dl	30.5 gm/dl*	32.5 - 35.2 gm/dl
MPV	13.2fl	9.8 fl	7.0 - 10.3 fl
RDW-CV	15.60%*	15.1 %	11.4 - 13.5%
PCV	38.1	29.1	38 - 47%
ESR	60 mm of fall @ the end 1st hr*	60 mm of fall @ the end 1st hr*	0 - 20 mm/h
Biochemistry			
Renal function test with electrolytes			
Blood urea	38 mg/dl	17 mg/dl	9 - 21 mg/dl
Serum creatinine	0.8 mg/dl	0.5 mg/dl	0.45 - 0.81 mg/dl
Sodium	139 mEq/L	146 mEq/L	132 - 141 mEq/L
Potassium	5.1mEq/L*	4.1 mEq/L	3.3 - 4.7 mEq/L
Serum calcium	7.6 mg/dl*	8.57 mg/dl*	9.2 - 10.5 mg/dl
Corrected calcium	Not carried out	9.13 mg/dl	
Phosphorus	1.4 mg/dl*	1.7 mg/dl*	3.6 - 5.6 mg/dl
Liver function test			
Serum bilirubin (total)	0.81 mg/dl	0.23 mg/dl	<0.8 mg/dl
Direct bilirubin	0.14 mg/dl	0.07 mg/dl	<0.2 mg/dl
SGOT/AST	35 IU/L	21 IU/L	14-35 IU/L
SGPT/ALT	49 IU/L	58 IU/L	9-24 IU/L
Total proteins	5.6 gm/dl*	6.0 gm/dl	6.0-8.0 gm/dl
Albumin	3.6 gm/dl	3.3 gm/dl*	3.6-5.2 gm/dl
Globulin	2.6 gm/dl	2.7 gm/dl	1.6 - 4.4 gm/dl
PT control	14.0 seconds	Not carried out	
PT Test	12.9 seconds	Not carried out	10.2-12.0 seconds
INR	0.92	0.96	0.93-1.10
LDH	537 IU/L*	345 IU/L*	170-283 IU/L
Plasma glucose random	69	123*	54 - 117 mg/dl
Serum uric acid	6.2 mg/dl	7.1 gm/dl	2.6-7.6 mg/dl
Other investigations			
Quantitative CRP	Not carried out	0.002 mg/L	< 8 mg/L
Serum Iron	56 ug /dL	Not carried out	31 - 168
Percentage of iron saturation	38.10%	Not carried out	20 - 50%
Serum transferrin	161 gm/l*	Not carried out	220-337 gm/l
TIBC	147ug/dl	Not carried out	250-425 ug/dl
Ferritin	528.9ng/ml	Not carried out	12.7-82.8 ng/ml

Folate	>20.0 ng/ml	Not carried out	1.8 - 8.8 ng/ml
B12	455 pg/ml	Not carried out	200 - 835 pg/ml
Vit D3 Total	11.01 ng/ml	Not carried out	> 20 ng/ml
IPTH	40.16 pg/ml	Not carried out	*
Cultures and Microbiology		Not carried out	
Urine culture	Sterile	Sterile	
Blood culture	Contaminants	Contaminants	
Sputum AFB sample 1	Negative	Negative	
Sputum AFB sample 2	Negative	Negative	
Sputum AFB sample 3	Negative	Not carried out	
Sputum AFB sample gene xpert	Negative	Not carried out	
Sputum AFB MTB PCR	Negative	Not carried out	
Gastro-jejunal aspirate for AFB 1	Negative	Not carried out	
Gastro-jejunal aspirate for AFB 2	Negative	Not carried out	
Serology		Not carried out	
Viral markers		Not carried out	
HIV1& HIV 2	Negative	Not carried out	
HbsAg	Negative	Not carried out	
Anti HCV	Negative	Not carried out	
HAV IgM	Negative	Not carried out	
Hormones		Not carried out	
Testosterone	35 ng/dl*	Not carried out	208.08 to 496.58 ng/dl
ACTH	10.8 pg/ml	Not carried out	9 - 52 pg/ml
Cortisol	48.99 mcg/dl*	16.8 mcg/dl	1 - 28 mcg/dl
T3	34.02 ng/dl*	27.99 ng/dl*	97.66–176.43 ng/dl
T4	4.07 ug/dl*	3.94 ug/dl*	5.01 - 8.28 ug/dl
TSH	2.37 mIU/ml	2.37 mIU/ml	0.47–3.41 mIU/ml
LH	<0.10 mIU/ml	Not carried out	< 0.1 - 3.7 mIU/ml
FSH	0.61mIU/ml	Not carried out	< 0.1 - 8.6 mIU/ml
Tumor markers			
CA 125	11.65 u/ml	Not carried out	< 35 U/ml
CA19.9	1.74 IU/ml	Not carried out	< 37 IU/ML
CEA	6.05 ng/ml*	Not carried out	< 3 ng/ml

* Deranged values are highlighted in bold

Based on above investigations a diagnosis of Disseminated Tuberculosis with secondary hypocortisolism was made.

Management:

In the light of above diagnosis, the following treatment was instituted:

- Tablet Olanzapine 2.5 mg OD
- Tab Escitalopram 10 mg OD
- Weight based Antitubercular drugs are per national guidelines [11,12]
- Tab Pyridoxine 20 mg once daily
- Tab Shelcal OD
- Tab Eltroxin 12.5 mcg OD

- Tab Folic acid 5 mg OD
- Tab Rantac 150 mg BD
- Tab Hydrocortisone 5 mg BD (planned for gradual tapering and stress protocol)

Patient was discharged after around 15 days of hospitalisation. Patient was followed up every month to monitor progress of his clinical condition.

He gradually started eating and gained weight, with exercise tolerance of 5 kms; and normal liver function tests. His evaluation after two months of completion of ATT revealed, he is cheerful, going to school, started studying, regularly eating homemade food and gained 22 kg of weight and his parents were also relieved of their anxiety.

Figure 1: Photograph of CECT chest abdomen done at the time of admission

Figure 2: Photographs of CECT chest done after 10 days

Discussion

Sudden pressure discrepancy between alveoli and bronchovascular sheath, mainly in the presence of alveolar overdistension is the probable cause of most cases of pneumomediastinum. [1] In tuberculosis spontaneous mediastinum is rare, but cases have been reported in both miliary as well as non miliary tuberculosis due to alveolar damage. Since, chest pain and dyspnea, two of the most

common presenting symptoms, of spontaneous pneumomediastinum have a very broad differential diagnosis; the diagnosis of spontaneous pneumomediastinum is more often than not extremely challenging and difficult.

Management of spontaneous pneumomediastinum which usually follows a benign course is conservative in most cases. [1] Atypical presentations of disseminated tuberculosis like

pneumomediastinum, though rare, can be seen in few cases of pulmonary TB with or without subcutaneous emphysema in miliary, non-miliary, and cavitary forms [13].

Pneumomediastinum occurring in tuberculosis is a very rare presentation of tuberculosis and can cause pose difficulties in management of the case [3]. Therefore, a high index of clinical suspicion of tuberculosis is invaluable; and should always be kept in mind in a young patient of acute spontaneous pneumomediastinum without history of trauma. Pneumomediastinum without subcutaneous emphysema in cavitary pulmonary tuberculosis makes our case a unique one. The CECT scan picture clearly depicted a communication of pulmonary cavity to the mediastinal cavity (caverno-pleuro-mediastinal fistula) in our case.

Conclusion

Our patient was a case of secondary hypocortisolism with low ACTH, possibly due to partial agenesis of pituitary glands who developed disseminated Tuberculosis and started responding to the treatment. He is presently on antitubercular drugs, low dose steroids and low dose levothyroxine as supplements. His secondary sexual organs are completely developed; endocrinology review workup is planned at a later date after completion of six months anti tubercular drugs. Tuberculosis presents variably and sometimes it is difficult to get microbiological evidence, though newer modalities of evaluation like genexpert, MTB PCR are available but in rare cases it is difficult to obtain samples and work up is still difficult. Obtaining proper history and clinical examination is of prime importance; as it can provide us some vital clues for diagnosis. Psychiatry patients or patients with depression make evaluation for tuberculosis extremely challenging.

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